

Transition Temperature of Heptahydrated Copper Sulphate

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Study of distribution coefficient of a morphologically analogous host having a greater range of stability with the guest at tracer level gives a prominent break at the transition temperature of the guest component¹. By this technique existence of a heptahydrated vitriol of copper was demonstrated through mixed crystal formation by earlier workers². The range of stability of the interesting compound is not, however, known. Heptahydrated cobalt sulphate $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken as host and copper sulphate in tracer level was used as the guest component. Homogeneous distribution coefficients were studied at different temperatures and the prominent break obtained at 13.5° has been argued to be due to the transition of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to its lower hydrate. Partition values indicate the possibility of isolation of the interesting compound in question. The new mode of approach in finding out the transition temperatures can be of great help in predicting the existence and the properties of unknown compounds.

A search in the old literature will reveal that the existence of copper sulphate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been shown only through mixed crystal formation with other heptahydrated vitriols like $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ². Nothing in details about this interesting compound is known to us. Failure in its isolation may be due to long range of stability of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is also comparatively less soluble than any other vitriols known to us. It may also so happen that the heptahydrated vitriols in question is metaastable with respect to the pentahydrated copper sulphate. Range of stability of heptahydrated salt is not known. The object of the present work is, therefore, two fold in nature, determination of the transition temperature of unknown compound in question by the method already developed¹ here and to have an idea about the order of solubility of unknown compound.

It was, therefore, decided to study the distribution coefficient of $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (host) and copper (guest) in $0.5 N \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ medium at different temperatures for determining the transition temperature of heptahydrated copper sulphate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobalt sulphate $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and copper sulphate $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and all other reagents used were of AnalaR variety. Weighed amount of solid cobalt sulphate, $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (ground to 120 mesh) together with a known amount of solid copper sulphate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and a known quantity of saturated cobalt sulphate solution in $0.5 N \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ at a particular temperature were equilibrated by shaking for 48 hrs in a sealed tube. The time required for equilibration was however found to be 24 hrs. Cobalt was determined as anhydrous cobalt sulphate, from the supernatant solution. Copper was deposited on platinum cathode, dissolved in HNO_3 and was estimated iodometrically, adding silver nitrate before the addition

1. B. C. Purkayastha and Samir Sarkar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 347.
2. J. W. Ratgers, *Zeit. Phy. Chem.*, 1894, **15**, 571; 1894, **16**, 583.

of potassium iodide to obtain a sharp end point. From the loss of initial concentration of copper in solution, the amount of copper in the solid phase was calculated. The method of determining the distribution coefficient was similar to that used by V. G. Khlopin³. The distribution coefficient, D , was then calculated from the following expression⁴ :—

$$\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{solid}} = D \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{solution}}$$

Variation of distribution coefficients with time are given in Fig. 1, which shows the time required for attainment of equilibrium at a particular temperature. Some typical results are recorded in Table 1.

Fig.1. Curve A & B: Distribution of Cu between $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals and its saturated solution in $0.5\text{N H}_2\text{SO}_4$ acid medium at 5°C (left hand side scale) and 33.0°C (right hand side scale) respectively showing the attainment of equilibrium.

DISCUSSION

The equilibrium between the host and the guest was attained by equilibrating almost equal amounts of solid surfaces in contact with the saturated solution of host component (cobalt sulphate) containing very trace amount of the guest component (copper).

In order to verify the constancy of the distribution factors, the amounts of the solid phases were varied and the results in Table I (a and b) show that the distribution factor is constant throughout the entire range of temperatures.

In the system under investigation, partition values are, however very favourable. The host component in question is highly soluble. Washings and other complexities were avoided in the similar way as were done in the previous communications¹. Average of three

- V. G. Khlopin and M. S. Merkulova, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR* 1949, **65**, 861, 1950, **71**, 689.
- L. M. Henderson and F. C. Kracek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 738.

TABLE 1

The distribution of traces of Cu between preformed $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals and its saturated solution in 0.5 N H_2SO_4 .

Conc. of Copper	Temp. (°C)	Fraction of cobalt in solid phase (%)	Fraction of copper in solid phase (%)	D
(a) $2.52 \times 10^{-2}M$	5	50.56	57.54	1.325
		39.00	45.75	1.319
		30.30	37.25	1.365
		20.84	25.75	1.317
		Av.	1.331	
(b) $1.74 \times 10^{-2}M$	33	40.07	33.62	0.758
		36.12	30.36	0.771
		30.11	24.92	0.770
		20.42	16.67	0.779
		Av.	0.770	
(c) $1.74 \times 10^{-2}M$	0	43.76	54.41	1.533
		44.20	54.41	1.507
		44.28	54.41	1.502
		Av.	1.514	
(d) $1.94 \times 10^{-2}M$	7	44.39	49.22	1.214
		44.59	49.22	1.204
		44.42	49.22	1.212
		Av.	1.210	
(e) $3.74 \times 10^{-2}M$	20	46.43	44.10	0.910
		46.78	44.46	0.910
		46.47	44.10	0.909
		Av.	0.910	
(f) $2.97 \times 10^{-2}M$	40	36.39	29.06	0.716
		34.45	27.15	0.709
		34.43	27.15	0.709
		Av.	0.711	

N.B. (a) Concentration of cobalt in the saturated solution of cobalt sulphate at 5° and 33° were respectively 1.64 and 2.62 molar.

(b) Experimental data as given in table 1 (a and b) show the constancy of the distribution factors both below and above the transition temperature of the guest component, whereas data (c to f) show values of distribution factors with nearly the same percentage of the solid phase both below and above the transition temperature of the guest component.

partition values at a particular temperature represents a point in the curve as shown in figure 2. A few typical data are shown in Table 1. The distribution values computed in this way at each temperature have been plotted against temperature in figure 2.

Fig.2. Study of transition point as determined from the variation of homogenous distribution coefficients at different temperatures.

A glance at the figure 2 will show that a sudden change takes place in the neighbourhood of 13.5°. As solubility of the host component plotted against temperature describes a smooth straight line course, the abrupt change in question should be attributed to the guest component undergoing transition at this particular temperature. In view of the fact that copper is taken up by cobalt sulphate, $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, through mixed crystal formation, composition of the guest component can be attributed to be $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the temperature referred to, can be ascribed, as the transition temperature of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It should not be out of place to mention that $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has never been isolated. Earlier workers have shown its existence only through mixed crystal formation^{2,5}. Its range of stability was, however, unknown to us. The new mode of approach has enabled us in finding out the range of stability. It can, therefore, be claimed that $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ cannot be isolated above 13.5°. Thus we have proved, the existence of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and have shown that the range of stability of the compound can be determined. Another important parameter on the isolation of a compound is the solubility of the unknown compound in question. If we assume, like Ratner⁶, that the ratio of the activity coefficient of the tracer and the carrier is near about unity, then $D = \frac{S}{S_1}$ where S and S_1 are the solubilities of the host and guest components in molar concentrations and D is the distribution coefficient. From our knowledge of solubility of $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ under identical condition (1.636 moles/lit. at 5°) and from the values of the distribution coefficient as determined by us, solubility of heptahydrated copper sulphate will be about 0.124 mol/lit. Solubility of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is less by a factor of 1.5.

5. H. W. Foote, *J. Amer. Chem.*, 1901, 25, 418.

6. A. P. Ratner, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, 1, 789.

It can, therefore, be inferred that $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may be crystallised below 13.5° from a supersaturated solution if the degree of supersaturation exceeds the solubility of pentahydrated $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by, say, a factor of 2. It may so happen that the unknown compound in question may be unstable in presence of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, as $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ⁷ is unstable in presence $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Appearance of pentahydrated blue vitriol should be avoided by all means. It should be specifically mentioned that distribution factors bear, however, a qualitative relation to solubilities, even in case of host and guest whose chemical properties are similar. Crystallographic forces and many other factors are responsible for the discrepancy but in closely chemically similar system as in case of binary electrolytes an approximate order of solubilities can be predicted.

It should be pointed out that at such low concentration of the guest component, host in question takes up the guest though mixed crystal formation even above the transition temperature of the guest component. A glance at Table 2 will reveal that even at 33° distribution coefficient comes out constant which give strong evidence that guest in question is incorporated in the host lattice through mixed crystal formation. It should further be noted that heptahydrated vitriols are dimorphous in nature. In certain cases orthorhombic variety is the stablest form and in other cases monoclinic forms are found to be the stable variety. Magnesium sulphate $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (orthorhombic) is the stablest of all the heptahydrated vitriols. Distribution measurements were made with copper as guest and $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as host at 5° , uptake was very low and it follows an adsorption pattern. From this study it can be inferred that probably orthorhombic variety of heptahydrated copper sulphate $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ does not exist even at 5° . In view of the fact that copper has been found to be taken up by heptahydrated cobalt sulphate $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which is stable in its monoclinic form and that the partition value for the system is higher than unity. It can be inferred that the stable variety of heptahydrated copper sulphate $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is also monoclinic in nature.

Before conclusion it should be pointed out that the new mode of approach in finding out the transition temperature through mixed crystal formation can be of great help in predicting the existence and properties of unknown compounds.

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7. E. Roger Washburn and W. Jack Clem, *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 754.